

HYBRID EDUCATION AND EDUCATIONAL NETWORKS: AN IVAN ILLICH PERSPECTIVE¹

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the theme of the deschooling of society proposed by Ivan Illich in his work *Deschooling Society* (1971), analyzing its visionary relevance to the contemporary educational landscape, particularly in the context of hybrid education and digital learning networks. Conducted as a bibliographic study, this research examines Illich's critique of the compulsory school system, which, according to him, perpetuates inequalities and suppresses the intrinsic capacity to learn, advocating for the abolition of the school's monopoly on education in favor of social deinstitutionalization. The study delves into the 'learning webs' idealized by Illich, conceived as decentralized and convivial alternatives that would allow for the free association of individuals in search of knowledge and the exchange of skills, without the coerciveness of a formal curriculum. It is argued that the advancement of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the internet has enabled the realization of this utopia, evidenced by the popularization of online platforms and the adoption of hybrid education models. Such models integrate face-to-face and remote instruction, creating digital learning ecologies that promote collaboration, student agency, and personalized learning. The concluding remarks highlight the bold and prescient nature of Illich's ideas, which, although they did not foresee specific technological evolutions, anticipated the need for collaborative education, pointing toward a current movement that suggests a society beyond schooling.

Keywords: Deschooling. Hybridization. Digital ecosystems. Learning communities. ICT.

1 INTRODUCTION

When the book *Deschooling Society* was published in 1971 by former Catholic priest Ivan Illich, it caused a major stir in the field of educational studies. It is worth noting that the 1960s and 1970s were marked by a wave of skepticism toward the institution of schooling, particularly following the publication of the Coleman Report, alongside new movements driven by sociology — such as the publication of Bourdieu and Passeron's *La Reproduction* — and the social movements of 1968. This social unrest prompted thinkers from various fields of knowledge to scrutinize schools and education as arenas of ideological struggle

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centering, ultimately, on social norms.

However, Deschooling Society became something it never intended to be. It was perceived by many as an unfair and haphazard critique of the institution of schooling, advocating — in the view of hasty readers — for the end of public education in favor of a predominantly private system. Indeed, the translation of the original English title into Portuguese (Sociedade sem Escolas [Society Without Schools]) carried an emotional weight that contributed to a biased interpretation of the text at best, or to the complete ostracism of the work at worst. It can be argued that Deschooling Society conceals far more than a mere proposal for a society without schools.

Illich posits as a fundamental premise modern society's addiction to the school system. He views it not merely as a perpetuator of the injustices and inequalities already present in society — as figures such as Bourdieu, Giroux, and Apple have argued in their respective fields — but as a mechanism capable of generating its own inequalities and imposing them upon the social order. Although Illich's perspective on schooling is far removed from the sentimental and affective manner in which we are accustomed to regarding it today — being stark and perhaps harsh — it cannot be dismissed out of hand.

What Illich proposes is not the end of schools — particularly public schools — but rather the social recognition of forms of education other than what is known as formal schooling. In this regard, in the 1970s, he outlined a utopian vision that today stands very close to concrete reality, primarily due to the advancement of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the internet. Illich advocated for the establishment of learning communities—which he termed 'learning webs' or networks—united by a common interest in one or more subjects, rather than by compulsory enrollment in a school system. These groups would connect with experts recognized in topics of collective interest and, through free association, establish a space for teaching and learning.

Today, through technological mediation, this utopia is fully realizable and is increasingly becoming a reality through platforms such as Khan Academy, Coursera, Brainly, Udemy, and EdX, among others. Social networks — another significant phenomenon in the digital information revolution — also facilitate such encounters and the formation of groups or collectives centered on common

interests. The formal education sector has responded to this movement by increasingly integrating ICT into its daily practices, culminating in the adoption of a hybrid education model that blends face-to-face instruction with online digital learning. This paper aims to address, from a conceptual standpoint, the issue of hybrid education and the learning communities envisioned in Illich's work. It proposes a reflection on the similarities and differences between the current context and what Illich proposed in the 1970s."

2 METHODOLOGY

This paper is characterized as a bibliographic research and review study. Methodologically, a bibliographic review 'involves the reading, analysis, and interpretation of books, journals, manuscripts, reports, theses, monographs, etc. (that is, in most cases, the products that consolidate the construction of scientific work)' (Mazucato, 2018, p. 69). A bibliographic review was chosen as a means to synthesize academic production on the subject, analyzing it critically to underpin the subsequent reflection."

3 DISCUSSION

3.1 The Deschooling of Society Proposed by Illich

It is important to note, as stated in the introduction, that Illich's work emerges from a context of profound mistrust toward the institution of schooling. Yet, this occurred simultaneously with the 1970s movement across much of the then so-called Third World to initiate large-scale and accelerated school inclusion, marked by the opening of new schools and the establishment of public policies aimed at mass schooling. Illich lived in both the United States and Latin America during this period, experiencing both realities firsthand.

For Illich, deschooling entails the abolition of compulsory public schooling and the monopoly that schools hold over education (Hartch, 2015; Illich, 2018). He argued that schooling and learning are concepts that have been erroneously conflated; indeed, schools often suppress the genuine capacity to learn. In Illich's

view, true learning should be a free and unconstrained pursuit undertaken by free individuals.

The concept of deschooling, as proposed by Illich, encompasses more than just formal education; it seeks the deinstitutionalization of society as a whole (Illich, 2018; Illich et al., 1973). Illich advocated for a revolution in educational structures to liberate the learner from the institutionalized context, thereby promoting a revitalization of individual autonomy and the capacity to learn (Illich et al., 1973).

At the individual level, Illich argued that schooling induced a series of cognitive and psychological distortions. It 'schools' the individual to confuse process with substance—that is, to conflate teaching with learning, grade advancement with education, and diplomas with competence (Illich, 2018). This led to the mistaken belief that 'the longer the schooling, the better the results' and that graduation is synonymous with success (Illich, 2018, p. 09).

In school, the student's imagination is conditioned to accept service in place of value, leading them to identify health with medical treatment, community welfare with social services, and productive work with competition (Hartch, 2015; Illich, 2018). This institutional dependence generated a 'psychological impotence,' rendering the individual incapable of organizing their own life based on personal experiences and resources, turning them into a docile and manipulatable consumer. According to Illich, schools 'indoctrinate citizens to believe that bureaucracies, guided by scientific knowledge, are efficient and benevolent,' which discourages cooperation and sharing while fostering alienation and competition (Illich, 2018).

For Illich, the experience of not 'succeeding' in the school system resulted in a 'new internalized sense of guilt for having failed,' stigmatizing the poor as inferior (Hartch, 2015; Illich, 2018; Illich; Cayley, 2007). Moreover, Illich believed that schooling stifled personal initiative and creativity, valuing only that which could be measured by an expert-conducted evaluation process or permitted by the established curriculum.

In Illich's view, educational institutions generate a series of serious negative consequences for both the individual and society, culminating in a widespread erosion of human values and capacities. From this perspective,

schools are not merely inefficient but actively harmful, serving a hidden purpose he described as the 'ritualization of progress' (Illich et al., 1973).

Nevertheless, Illich's thought on deschooling has frequently been subject to misinterpretation. A primary misconception lies in the belief that he opposed schools entirely or was against learning itself (Hartch, 2015). In reality, Illich did not oppose the existence of schools, provided they were acknowledged as 'privileged enclaves' and did not monopolize public choice (Illich; Cayley, 2007). His critique targeted compulsory attendance and excessive institutionalization rather than traditional teaching methods in themselves—particularly when student motivation was present (Hartch, 2015).

Another common criticism concerned an alleged lack of concrete alternatives to the existing school system (Hartch, 2015). Illich, however, viewed his role as that of a social diagnostician, leaving the task of developing specific political programs to others. Some critics labeled him a romantic or a reactionary seeking a return to the past (Illich; Cayley, 2007). Illich refuted this view, asserting that his historical analysis aimed to enhance the understanding of the present rather than to revive archaic forms of social organization. He acknowledged that the incidental education of the past could not simply be replicated; instead, it required conscious design suited to contemporary society (Illich, 2018; Illich; Cayley, 2007).

3.2 Illich's Learning Webs and Networks

In the thought of Ivan Illich, learning webs or networks are conceived as a radical alternative to compulsory schooling. They aim for a society in which learning is facilitated and accessible to all, at any stage of life, rather than being monopolized by institutions comprised of bureaucracies guided by scientific knowledge (Illich, 2018). These learning webs seek to overturn the limiting and exclusionary logic of the compulsory school system by promoting self-direction, personal initiative, and mutual cooperation.

According to Illich, an ideal educational system should serve three main purposes: (I) to provide all who want to learn with access to available resources at any time in their lives; (II) to empower those who wish to share what they know to

find those who wish to learn; and (III) to furnish all who wish to present an issue to the public with the opportunity to make their challenge known (Illich, 2018; Illich et al., 1973). Thus, interconnected, decentralized, and organic networks are organized, based no longer on coercion and compulsion, but on the capacity for the free association of individuals.

These networks are conceived to be 'convivial,' a concept Illich contrasts with the 'manipulative' institutions predominant in modern society. Whereas manipulative institutions impose services and products, convivial ones are modest, facilitating communication and spontaneous cooperation, with few rules and minimal administrative structures (Hartch, 2015; Illich, 2018).

Illich proposed four categories of learning webs to achieve this vision, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 – Categories of Learning Webs/Networks

Characteristic / Network	Description	Objective
Reference Services to Educational Objects	Aims to facilitate access to "things or processes used for formal learning."	To demonopolize educational materials that schools have made expensive and restricted.
Skill Exchanges	Allows persons to list their skills, specifying the conditions under which they are willing to serve as models for others who want to learn them.	To offer generalized academic freedom to protect the right to teach any skill.
Peer-Matching	A communications network which permits persons to describe the learning activity in which they wish to engage, in the hope of finding partners for the inquiry.	To identify individuals based on a mutual desire to discuss a book, film, or theme, for example, leaving the initiative for the meeting to the individual.
Reference Services to Educators-at-Large	A directory of professionals, paraprofessionals, and freelancers who can offer their services.	To guide and mentor, providing criticism and assistance in intellectual journeys, rather than imposing a curriculum.

Source: Author's own elaboration with data from (Illich, 2018)

The configuration of Illich's learning webs is deeply rooted in his libertarian pedagogical perspective, reflecting the desire — as previously expressed — for an anti-institutional revolution. It is important to clarify that this study seeks to

briefly outline Illich's thought regarding the deschooling of society as a means to understand his vision of learning webs, while refraining from passing value judgments on the content of his critique.

In this regard, it is worth noting that even Illich quickly recognized that his book could have 'unwanted side effects' (Illich; Cayley, 2007). He published an article in *The Saturday Review*—which he considered the 'major criticism' of his own book—warning that the mistake would be to believe that schools were the only technique for creating and entrenching the 'myth of education,' for there were 'many other ways in which we can transform the world into a huge universal classroom' (Illich; Cayley, 2007, p. 59).

3.3 Hybrid Education as a Proposal

The advancement of ICT has enabled a social revolution in which individuals increasingly find themselves immersed in a world deeply dependent on digital electronic devices connected to a global information and communication network. It would be naive to assume that the field of education would remain unaffected by this paradigm shift regarding technology.

Indeed, albeit with some delay, various educational institutions — ranging from basic education (K-12) to higher education — already recognize that education without technological support is impossible in the 21st century. However, no educational modality has been more successful in incorporating ICT than Distance Education, particularly in Brazil, where numerous courses are planned and implemented with the explicit support of these technologies. The adoption of technological resources has driven exponential growth in enrollment numbers for this modality, allowing it to reach students inaccessible to conventional face-to-face educational institutions.

The widespread adoption of Distance Education (DE) has given rise to a movement seeking to understand the potential of applying its elements to face-to-face teaching. Thus, a new field of educational study has emerged, dedicated to understanding what has been conventionally termed Hybrid Education—that is, the application of DE elements in face-to-face instruction and vice versa.

Although we agree with Moran (2015), who indicates that education is

always a mixture of diverse elements—and therefore inherently hybrid—it is the merging of DE elements that justifies the terminology 'Hybrid Education' as a new movement within the educational context. But what are the characteristics of this new proposal? First, the convergence between face-to-face and DE opens new opportunities for the teaching process to take place not only in the physical, synchronous environment but also within the digital space, characterized by virtuality and asynchrony.

The student gains access to a 'virtual classroom,' which can be configured as an extension of the physical classroom or even as a fully autonomous space where new experiences can be lived. Diverse digital resources also facilitate new methodological configurations; that is, they allow the educator to explore new ways of teaching by adopting one or more strategies. We highlight interaction with virtual reality, augmented reality, simulators, and artificial intelligence itself as enhancers of new methodological approaches or as maximizers of the reach of well-known strategies, such as the flipped classroom, gamification, or project-based learning.

3.4 ICT, Hybrid Education, and Digital Learning Networks

The potential of hybrid education lies not only in enriching face-to-face classes with technological elements commonly found in Distance Education, but in creating a new space with its own interactive potential. This interaction is not limited to that between the subject and the technology, but extends to the various subjects utilizing it. Through the convergence enabled by the hybrid education proposal, the student becomes immersed in an omnidirectional communicative relationship, acting as both a receiver and a producer of information, knowledge, and culture. This effectively breaks away from the static, isolationist paradigm of conventional face-to-face teaching, where the student is merely a vessel into which curricular content is deposited.

Unlike its physical counterpart, the virtual classroom lacks well-defined boundaries; it is immersed in cyberspace and relates to other environments, spaces, and groups in a synergy of mutual exchange. Thus, a new networked (digital) ecology is configured, enabling new and more interactive learning

experiences.

According to Dias-Trindade (2020a; 2020b), these new learning ecologies can be conceptualized as open, complex, and adaptive systems, composed of dynamic and interdependent elements whose diversity allows for constant adaptation to their environment. This way of conceiving the educational process frames it as a flexible, open, and hybrid space, understanding teaching and learning as a living system that constructs, adapts, and transforms itself according to the needs of all its participants (Dias-Trindade, 2020a).

In the digital context, learning ecologies manifest as a paradigm for future educational systems, broadly supported by ICT. They tend to promote learning personalization by diversifying opportunities, experiences, and resources based on students' needs and interests (Islas; Carranza, 2017). In this environment, learning occurs dynamically, in a state of constant evolution and fluidity, blending face-to-face and virtual, as well as formal and non-formal spaces (Bezerra; Farias; Sousa, 2024; Dias-Trindade, 2020).

A space is also opened for collaboration among members of diverse networks who come together due to common interests or projects. In this way, the virtual classroom joins a broad, interconnected network of other classrooms and spaces, facilitating interaction among subjects. Hybrid education is already facilitating such spaces, breaking through physical limitations via internet connectivity; teachers and students find themselves immersed in new environments that favor open and collaborative learning. This new reality allows for student agency; the student, as previously mentioned, ceases to be a passive figure and begins to interact not only with the object of knowledge but with the ways in which that knowledge is mediated.

CONCLUSIONS

Although Illich's critique of schooling may have been harsh, one cannot fail to acknowledge his bold and visionary nature in proposing, in *Deschooling Society*, the concept of learning webs or networks. More than four decades later, these concepts would be, to some extent, adopted through hybrid or online education models. Illich did not anticipate a specific technological evolution—as

he designed his networks to function with the technologies available in his time—but rather the necessity for a collaborative form of education that would follow the exhaustion of individualistic, competitive educational models.

Contemporary technological progress increasingly propels us into cyberspace, making us more dependent on and influenced by what Pierre Lévy termed Cyberculture. The deschooling proposed by Illich is, in a way, taking shape and unfolding in today's society through the recognition and valuation of new spaces for teaching and learning. The popularization of self-paced courses and flexible learning paths, at the expense of rigid, closed curricula, may signal that we are moving not toward a society without schools, but toward a society beyond schooling.

The integration of hybridization into face-to-face courses is already a subject of discussion as a means to modernize teaching models, particularly in higher education. The COVID-19 pandemic, with its emergency remote teaching—though implemented haphazardly—served as a massive experiment for institutions to rethink approaches bridging face-to-face and distance education; the results of this experience are currently being measured. Furthermore, there remains a necessity for the student to be capable of lifelong learning, seizing opportunities to acquire new knowledge—a process facilitated by ICT, the internet, and hybridization.

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